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Dynamics of a Hollow Sphere Partially Filled with a Fluid

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Declaration by the Guide

This is to certify that this term paper entitled “Dynamics of a Hollow Sphere Partially Filled with a Fluid” has been done by Spandan Bhattacharya, 20PMC09 towards fulfilment of B.Sc. degree course during the year 2022-2023 under the guidance of Dr Vignesh G, Department of Physics, St. Joseph’s College(Autonomous).

Signature of the Guide

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Abstract

In this paper, we explore the dynamics of a hollow sphere partially filled with some fluid, in this case water. Compared to an empty hollow sphere, the bounciness of the sphere is weirdly affected when some fluid is introduced inside it. We experimentally observe the variation of coefficient of restitution of the sphere with the volume of fluid inside it. From this, we can determine how for what volume of a fluid, the loss of energy is maximum and what factors affect this loss of energy.

INDEX

Serial No.	Contents	PAGE NO.
1.	Introduction	6
2.	Coefficient of Restitution	7
3.	How is the energy lost?	8
4.	Shifting of Center of Mass of the System	9
5.	Calculation of Center of Mass of the System	10
6.	Experimental Setup	12
7.	Variation of Center of Mass with Height of Fluid	13
8.	Significance of Center of Mass	13
9.	Coefficient of Restitution and Height of Fluid	14
10.	Data Table	15
11.	Comparison of 0% volume of water and 100% volume of water	16
12.	Maximum Loss of Energy	18
13.	Factors Affecting the Energy Loss	19
14.	Application	20
15.	Bibliography	21

1. Introduction

Experimentally, it has been observed that the motion of the sphere containing fluid creates a jet formation. Initially when the sphere is dropped, the whole system of sphere and fluid behaves like one. We can understand this easily by comparing the center of mass of the system (fluid and sphere) and the center of mass of the hollow sphere alone. When the center of mass of the system is shifted from the original center of mass of the sphere, we observe this jet formation of the fluid.

Fig.1 Jet formation of fluid

The rebound height is significantly lowered when the sphere is partially filled with some fluid. We can obviously understand that a part of the initial potential energy of the system is lost in each bounce. Experimentally it has been seen that is loss happens during the second bounce. Various factors affect how much energy is lost, such as density of the fluid, volume of the fluid, surface tension.

2. Coefficient of Restitution

Coefficient of restitution (denoted by e) is basically a number lesser than 1, that gives you the measure of how much energy is lost during a collision. Mathematically, it can be expressed as a ratio of height, velocity, or even energy.

In terms of velocity, we can write:

$$e = \frac{|relative\ velocity\ after\ collision|}{|relative\ velocity\ before\ collision|}$$

In terms of height, we can write:

$$e = \sqrt{\frac{bounce\ height}{drop\ height}}$$

And in terms of energy loss fraction we can write:

$$e = \sqrt{1 - \frac{energy\ loss}{initial\ energy}}$$

3. How is the energy lost?

When the hollow sphere, partially filled with some fluid is dropped, initially the system acts as one and strikes the ground. During this journey, the fluid gets coupled to the sphere. The reaction force experienced by this system is the total change in momentum per unit time. In case of a completely empty hollow sphere, it is quite easy to imagine how the sphere bounces. The forces acting on it, the change of potential energy and kinetic energy is easy to calculate and visualize. The complication happens when the system is not uniform, in the sense that now it is partially filled with some fluid. In this case, most of the energy is lost due to the jet formation of the fluid. Energy is invested into the deformation of the fluid; thus, the value of COR is reduced greatly.

Fig2. Rebound and jet formation of a fluid-filled sphere by Taylor W. Killian, Robert A. Klaus, and Tadd T. Truscott

4. Shifting of Center of Mass of the System

For an empty hollow sphere, the center of mass of the system is at the geometric center. When some fluid is introduced inside the sphere, the center of mass of this new system is lowered. The center of mass goes down up to a certain point and then it comes back to the initial position again. From this we understand that there are two situations when the center of mass of the system is at the geometric center of the hollow sphere. First, the center of mass is at the geometric center when the sphere is completely empty. Again, it is at the geometric center when the sphere is completely filled with the fluid.

Fig.3 Lowering of Center of Mass

5. Calculation of Center of Mass of the System

For a given volume of fluid inside the sphere, the position of center of mass of the system can be calculated very easily.

Fig. 4 Determination of Center of Mass

Referring to the Fig. 4, we can calculate how much the center of mass has been lowered.

We know that the equation of center of mass of a two-body system along y-axis can be expressed by:

$$\text{CoM}_z = (m_1 z_1 + m_2 z_2) / (m_1 + m_2) \quad (1)$$

For our calculations, we note that:

1. The vertical diameter ranges from -R to +R and the center is at zero.
2. Height of the fluid cap is z.
3. Thickness of the sphere is (R₀ - R).

Volume of a cap of a sphere is given by:

$$V = (1/3)\pi(3R - h)h^2 \quad (2)$$

Here, R is the radius of the sphere and h is the height of the cap.

Fig. 5 volume of cap of a sphere

If ρ_0 is the density of the sphere, then mass of the sphere would be:

$$m_1 = (4/3)(\pi(R_0 - R)^3) \rho_0 \quad (3)$$

If ρ is the density of the fluid, then mass of the fluid can be found using equation (2) as:

$$m_2 = \rho V \quad (4)$$

Using these equations, we determine the center of mass of the system of fluid and hollow sphere as:

$$CoM = \frac{0.75(2R^2z^2 - z^4 - R^4)}{2R^3 + 3R^2z - z^3 + \frac{\rho_0}{\rho}(R_0^3 - R^3)}$$

6. Experimental Setup

1. Liquid: water at room temperature. Density = 1000kg/m^3
2. Material of the ball: ABS plastic. Density = 1060kg/m^3 to 1080kg/m^3
3. Inner radius of the ball, $R = 1.927\text{ cm}$
4. Outer radius of the ball, $R_0 = 1.988\text{ cm}$
5. Thickness of the ball, $(R_0 - R) = 0.61\text{ mm}$

Fig. 6 Setup for the Experiment

6.1 Variation of Center of Mass with height of fluid

Referring to the data mentioned above and putting the values in the equation of center of mass of the system of partially filled sphere, we obtained the following plot of center of mass vs height of fluid.

Fig. 7 Center of Mass Vs height

6.2 Significance of Center of Mass

The lowering of coefficient of restitution or loss of energy only happens when there is a relative change in position of center of mass of the hollow sphere and the center of mass of the system of partially filled sphere. More is the relative change in position of these two points, more is the energy lost.

This leads us to the realization that we can imagine the fluid to be another sphere/ball inside our hollow sphere. When we drop the whole system, their positions of center of mass remains unchanged, that is, there is no relative motion between the center of mass of the hollow sphere and the center of mass of the partially fluid-filled sphere. Only upon receiving the reaction force from the ground, the smaller sphere (actually fluid) moves independently inside the sphere, thus shifting the center of mass of the partially fluid-filled sphere and creating a relative motion between the two centers of masses. This motion does not contribute to the bouncing; hence some energy is lost here. The movement of the smaller ball is the degree of deformation of the fluid, which results in the jet formation inside the sphere and steals away energy from the system.

7. Coefficient of Restitution and Volume of Fluid

Another measure of the energy loss can be understood by observing the change of coefficient of restitution with respect to the volume of water used. From experimental data, a plot of coefficient of restitution vs volume of fluid has been obtained.

Fig. 8 Coefficient of Restitution vs Volume % of water

From this data, we see that for a given fluid (here water), maximum energy is lost when the volume of the fluid is around 50% of the total volume.

8. Data Table:

% of water filled	Drop Height, h_0 (cm)	Rebound Height, h_1 (cm)	$\sqrt{h_1/h_0} = e$	Coefficient of Restitution, e
0%	31.87	26.55	0.912	0.899
	41.73	33.80	0.899	
	50.40	39.77	0.888	
20%	41.3	24.64	0.772	0.756
	50.3	26.41	0.724	
	60.07	36.06	0.774	
50%	30.3	5.8	0.437	0.408
	39.5	5.1	0.359	
	50.5	8.3	0.405	
	65.7	12.3	0.432	
80%	30.2	10.2	0.581	0.716
	39.8	19.8	0.705	
	49.4	27.8	0.750	
	61.6	29.8	0.695	
100%	29.6	27.4	0.962	0.907
	41.2	33.3	0.899	
	51.6	39.4	0.873	
	59.2	47.5	0.895	

Fig. 9 Complete data of the experiment

9. Comparison of 0% volume of water and 100% volume of water.

Fig. 10 Rebound height vs Drop height (0% volume)

When the sphere is completely empty, coefficient of restitution is almost equal to 0.844, meaning very little energy is lost. Since there is no fluid in it, the center of mass of the system is not shifted from its initial position, that is the geometric center of the sphere. During the whole process of bouncing, there is no relative motion between the two centers of masses (center of mass with fluid, and center of mass without fluid) because we don't have any fluid inside it in the first place. Hence, with zero relative motion between the centers of masses, the energy lost is minimal.

Fig. 12 Rebound height vs Drop height (100% volume)

At 100% volume of water, that is when the sphere is completely filled with water, then coefficient of restitution is equal to 0.907, which is again almost equal to 1. The difference in the experimental value of COR at 0% volume of water and COR at 100% volume of water is only 0.008, which is extremely small.

Again, looking from the perspective of center of masses, there is no relative motion between the two centers of masses, thus implying that energy loss is again minimal.

This proves our theoretical analysis and establishes that for both fully filled and completely empty, the energy loss during the bounce is the minimum.

10. Maximum loss of energy

It is observed that the maximum loss in energy happens when the volume of the fluid is 50% of the total volume. It is also observed that the center of mass of the system drops down maximum at this particular volume of water. So, one can conclude that for a given fluid, maximum energy is lost at when it is halfway filled.

Fig. 13 Rebound height Vs Drop height (50% volume)

The coefficient of restitution for 50% volume of water is found to be 0.408, which is the lowest.

11. Factors affecting the energy loss

There are various factors affecting the energy loss. They are listed below:

1. Percentage of liquid filled:

Lesser or more the percentage of liquid filled, lesser is the energy loss, and for some critical intermediate percentage, the energy loss is maximum, and the critical volume percentage depends on other parameters like density ratio.

2. Density ratio (sphere to fluid):

Lesser is the density ratio, lesser is the critical volume percentage and more is the density ratio, more is the critical volume percentage.

3. Viscosity of liquid:

Viscous fluids are stickier. Hence, they tend to deform less compared to less viscous fluids. As a result, energy won't be expended in the deformation and loss of energy would be less.

4. Surface tension:

Surface tension of the fluid also affects the energy loss. More is the surface tension; less is the deformation of the fluid. Hence, energy loss is less.

12. Application

The deformation of the fluid inside a container happens due to some external force. Consequently, there is a subsequent motion of the fluid, much like an oscillation. This phenomenon can be used shock absorbers in tall buildings to protect them from earthquakes. If there is some sort of a large tank at the top of the building, then it can be filled with fluid which would absorb the impact of the earthquake. Much like in our experiment, energy would be lost in the deformation of the fluid, and act as shock absorber. This dampening system can be incorporated in sports technology and marine engineering to stabilize various systems.

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